

The Effect of Leadership, Education, and Work Stress on Employee Performance (Case Study at Technical Implementation Unit of Bekasi Hajj Dormitory)

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Abstract:- The implementation of good governance (Good Corporate Governance). One of the efforts in controlling Good Corporate Governance is by conducting a mental revolution in employees so that they can continue to innovate over time and environmental dynamics as well as advances in science. So that in this study discusses the problem of employee quality and employee performance, with a focus on research on the influence of leadership, education, and work stress, on employee performance in the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory Technical Implementation Unit. This study aims to determine the effect of leadership, education, and job stress on employee performance, using the quantitative method of causality where it can be seen that the relationship between variables to the object under study is more cause and effect so that in this study there are dependent variables and independent variables with a population of all employees at Technical Implementation Unit of Bekasi Hajj Dormitory.

Keywords:- Leadership, Education, and Work Stress.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of the national and international strategic environment faced by the Indonesian state at this time and in the future is a paradigm shift in the company or government, renewal of the institutional system, improvement of the competence of human resources in organizing and building the nation as well as relations between nations that lead to the implementation of Good Corporate Governance. Thus, the government or the private sector is required to prepare productive human resources in order to survive in the conditions of facing the global challenges faced.

Organizations in government such as Technical Implementation Unit of Bekasi Hajj Dormitory need to improve employee performance in order to achieve the vision and mission of the organization properly. Employee performance can be measured by looking at the influence of leadership, education, and work stress. There are a few variables that influence execution, specifically, capacity and ability, information and work arranging, identity, representative work inspiration, administration authority, organizational / company culture, worker work fulfillment, work environment, worker dependability, commitment, and teach from representatives and the organization [1].

There is value of the Results of Environmental Sanitation Monitoring and Health Protocols in the 2019-2021 Environmental Health Inspection conducted by the Bandung Class II Port Health Office and the results show that the Technical Implementation Unit of Bekasi Hajj Dormitory continues to experience a decrease in the value of dormitory health, water sanitation health, and sewage treatment. There is vector control that has increased in 2021. The results of the evaluation conducted by the Port Health Office stated that up to employees of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory did not fully understand environmental health. This is due to the lack of training and socialization related to the care and maintenance of good environmental health.

Based on the results of the January 2020–June 2022 Delay Recapitulation, it shows that with the relatively high number of employees who are late for work to reach 25% more than the total number of employees and the average delay time continues to increase every year until the average reaches 30 minutes. In addition, there are work programs/activities that do not exist from 2019 to 2021 at the Technical Implementation Unit of Bekasi Hajj Dormitory So far education and training are only in the form of financial agencies/institution training carried out by other agencies / institutions or units.

In a number of employees at the Technical Implementation Unit of Bekasi Hajj Dormitory, which has the most relatively many employees, it has a relatively small area compared to other Hajj Dormitory UPTs. In addition, based on a pre-survey that has been conducted on respondents as many as 30 employees. The results of the pre-survey can be seen that the indications that affect employee performance at the Technical Implementation Unit of Bekasi Hajj Dormitory are factors of leadership, education, and work stress.

The author also completes the data obtained by conducting interviews with the leadership and several employees at Technical Implementation Unit of Bekasi Hajj Dormitory. The results of the author's interview with the leadership found that the leadership also realized that many things must be improved in the management of the Technical Implementation Unit of Bekasi Hajj Dormitory.

II. LITERATURE

A. Human Resource Management

Human asset administration could be a handle in getting, preparing, surveying and compensating each representative, whereas too paying consideration to the employee's possess business relationship, as well as well-being, security, and decency [2]. Based on the above theory, human resource management can be categorized as a process to give rights to employees and give the best attention to the company. Human asset administration can too be characterized as science and craftsmanship that relates the relationship and part of labor to be successful and productive in utilizing human capacities in arrange to realize certain objectives [3].

B. Leadership

Leadership is a term that connotes a strong and dynamic image of an individual, where the individual successfully leads a group in a particular field. Whereas in other opinions, leadership can be said to be a persuasive process towards others to understand and agree with what the individual is doing and makeup how the task is performed effectively. In the process, there are efforts to facilitate individual and collective efforts to achieve common goals.

C. Education

Education is a duplication of an individual's ability to complete a certain job. With certain levels of education, the individual or employee is considered capable and capable to carry out their duties. Training is an effort to increase the knowledge and skills of employees in overcoming work. Performance can be improved if there is an increase in employee skills, knowledge, insights, and attitudes. So the correlation between education and training and employee performance is interrelated, where education and training are realized in a structured and systematic manner.

D. Work Stress

Work stress is defined as the process by which the emotional state of the individual arises due to a mismatch between the workload and the individual's ability to deal with pressure [4]. Based on the theory of previous experts, it can also be interpreted that work stress is a condition where there is tension or imbalance of thoughts caused by external and internal factors where it affects the quality of work carried out by employees and affects both physical and psychic.

E. Employee Performance

Employee performance is an appreciation of work, where usually a great thing in terms of quality and in terms of the amount accomplished per unit of a certain period of time with the duty given to the person [5]. Performance can too be characterized as the set of all comes about delivered on a particular work or action amid a particular period [6].

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Based on previous research, the framework developed in the research is as follows.

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework

Based on the picture above, there are seven hypotheses in this study, namely:

H1: Leadership affects the performance of employees of the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory.
 H2: Education affects the performance of employees of the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory.
 H3: Work stress affects the performance of employees of the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory.
 H4: Leadership, education, and work stress simultaneously affect the performance of employees of the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory.

IV. RESEARCH AND METHODS

In this study, the authors used a quantitative statistical analysis method, namely on a survey scale to express the weight ratio between variables and other variables. The author distributed a questionnaire to all staff of the technical implementation unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory, totaling 114 people for analysis. Analyzing the data, the authors used the Partial Least Square (PLS) - Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique with SmartPLS 3.0 to validate structural measurements and models.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The respondents' characteristic data was obtained from a questionnaire that had been distributed to all employees in the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory, totaling 114 people. The following are the results of the data analysis that has been carried out.

Variabel	Item	Hitung	Tabel	keterangan
Kepemimpinan (X1)	Pembinaan Hubungan Kerja			
	A.a.	0,446	0,423	Valid
	A.b.	0,714	0,423	Valid
	A.c.	0,691	0,423	Valid
	Efektivitas			
	B.a.	0,462	0,423	Valid
	B.b.	0,618	0,423	Valid
	B.c.	0,651	0,423	Valid
	Partisipatif			
	C.a.	0,549	0,423	Valid
	C.b.	0,877	0,423	Valid
	C.c.	0,842	0,423	Valid
	Mendelagaskan Tugas dan Waktu			
	D.a.	0,455	0,423	Valid
	D.b.	0,741	0,423	Valid
D.c.	0,720	0,423	Valid	
Pendidikan (X2)	Pendidikan			
	A.a.	0,714	0,423	Valid
	A.b.	0,741	0,423	Valid
	A.c.	0,494	0,423	Valid
	Pelatihan			
	B.a.	0,456	0,423	Valid
	B.b.	0,842	0,423	Valid
	B.c.	0,434	0,423	Valid
	Pengalaman Kerja			
C.a.	0,720	0,423	Valid	
C.b.	0,495	0,423	Valid	
C.c.	0,842	0,423	Valid	
Stress Kerja (X3)	Beban Kerja			
	A.a.	0,551	0,423	Valid
	A.b.	0,439	0,423	Valid
	A.c.	0,485	0,423	Valid
	Konflik Peran			
	B.a.	0,666	0,423	Valid
	B.b.	0,489	0,423	Valid
	B.c.	0,849	0,423	Valid
	Ambiguitas Peran			
	C.a.	0,789	0,423	Valid
	C.b.	0,443	0,423	Valid
	C.c.	0,462	0,423	Valid
	Burnout			
	D.a.	0,461	0,423	Valid
	D.b.	0,764	0,423	Valid
D.c.	0,694	0,423	Valid	
Kinerja Pegawai (Y)	Jumlah Pekerjaan			
	A.a.	0,716	0,423	Valid
	A.b.	0,757	0,423	Valid
	A.c.	0,720	0,423	Valid
	Kualitas Pekerjaan			
	B.a.	0,855	0,423	Valid
	B.b.	0,555	0,423	Valid
	B.c.	0,525	0,423	Valid
	Ketepatan Waktu			
	C.a.	0,790	0,423	Valid
	C.b.	0,673	0,423	Valid
	C.c.	0,811	0,423	Valid
	Kehadiran			
	D.a.	0,526	0,423	Valid
	D.b.	0,455	0,423	Valid
D.c.	0,466	0,423	Valid	
Kemampuan Kerjasama				
E.a.	0,869	0,423	Valid	
E.b.	0,444	0,423	Valid	
E.c.	0,519	0,423	Valid	

Table 1: Validity Test Results

Validity tests are carried out to measure whether the data obtained in the study is valid data or not, with the data collection tool (instrument) used is a questionnaire. The minimum requirement of an instrument is considered valid if its validity index value has a r calculate > r table. Based on the data in the table above, the validity of the research instrument (questionnaire) with each statement in can be that the r calculate value is greater than 0.423 so that the whole is declared valid.

Variabel	Rata-rata	Simpangan Baku	Maks.	Min.	L Hitung	L Tabel	Kesimpulan
Kepemimpinan (X1)	42,111	3,617	2,688	0,047	2,688	1,950	L Hitung > L Tabel, hasilnya normal
Pendidikan (X2)	35,130	2,191	2,623	0,003	2,623	1,950	L Hitung > L Tabel, hasilnya normal
Stress Kerja (X3)	42,241	3,161	2,211	0,033	2,211	1,950	L Hitung > L Tabel, hasilnya normal
Kinerja (Y)	51,519	3,347	2,638	0,047	2,638	1,950	L Hitung > L Tabel, hasilnya normal

Table 2: Normality Test

Normality tests are useful for determining data that has been obtained as normal as possible or taken from normal populations. A good regression model is to have a normal or close to normal distribution, by looking at a histogram that compares observational data with a distribution that is close to normal. Based on the table above, the results of the normality test using excel found that the variables leadership (X1), education (X2), and work stress (X3) as well as performance variables (Y) stated that L calculate > L table, it is stated that the instrument used is normal.

Inner VIF Values				
	KEPEMIMPINAN (X1)	KINERJA (Y)	PENDIDIKAN (X2)	STRESS KERJA (X3)
KEPEMIMPINAN (X1)		2,001		
PENDIDIKAN (X2)		1,773		
STRESS KERJA (X3)		1,570		
KINERJA (Y)				

Table 3. Multicollinearity test

Multicollinearity tests are used to test correlations between independent variables or dependent variables in regression models. Based on the table above, the results of the multicollinearity test using SEM PLS found that the variables of leadership (X1), education (X2), and work stress (X3) were stated that the VIF value < 10, it was stated that all independent variables did not occur multicollinearity.

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95,0%	Upper 95,0%
Intercept	-0,500	4,156	-0,120	0,905	-8,847	7,847	-8,847	7,847
X1	-0,023	0,042	-0,557	0,580	-0,107	0,061	-0,107	0,061
X2	0,039	0,077	0,511	0,611	-0,115	0,193	-0,115	0,193
X3	0,062	0,075	0,829	0,411	-0,088	0,212	-0,088	0,212

Table 4: Heterochedasticity test

The heterochedasticity test is used to test regression models in the event of variance dissimilarity from the residual of one observation to another [7]. Based on the table above, the results of the heterochedasticity test using excel found that the variables leadership (X1), education (X2), and work stress (X3) were stated that the P-Value value > 0.05, it was stated that all independent variables had no problem with heterochedasticity.

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	r Kritis	Keterangan
Kepemimpinan (X1)	0,711	0,60	Reliabel
Pendidikan (X2)	0,821	0,60	Reliabel
Stress Kerja (X3)	0,922	0,60	Reliabel
Kinerja (Y)	0,602	0,60	Reliabel

Table 5: Reliability test

Reliability tests are used to test the reliability of data on research. Based on the table above, the reliability test shows that all variables have a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient above 0.60, so it can be stated that all variable measurements from the questionnaire used are reliable, meaning that the questionnaire used in this study is a reliable questionnaire or research technique with accuracy and accuracy.

Path Coefficients

Mean, STDEV, T-Values, P-Values

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (tO/STDEV)	P Values
Kepemimpinan (X1) -> Kinerja (Y)	0,324	0,326	0,086	3,748	0,000
Pendidikan (X2) -> Kinerja (Y)	0,597	0,590	0,080	7,497	0,000
Stress Kerja (X3) -> Kinerja (Y)	-0,065	-0,079	0,080	0,814	0,416

Table 6: Direct Effects

Multiple linear regression analysis was performed to test the direction and how much influence independent variables have on dependent variables [8]. Based on the table above, the results of the regression analysis can be obtained with the following regression equation:

$$Y = 0,324 X1 + 0,597 X2 - 0,065 X3$$

From the mathematical equation of such multiple linear regression can be concluded as follows:

- The coefficient b1 is positive (0.324), then there is a unidirectional relationship between X1 and Y.
- The coefficient b2 is positive (0.597), then there is a unidirectional relationship between X2 and Y.
- The coefficient b3 is negative (-0.065), then there is an opposite relationship between X3 and Y.

In addition to this explanation, based on table 6, it can also be seen that the education variable (X2) is the most dominant variable, as evidenced by the regression coefficient value of 0.597, meaning that education has a large role compared to leadership and work stress in influencing the improvement of employee performance at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory.

Variabel	Kepemimpinan	Kinerja	Pendidikan	Stress Kerja
Kepemimpinan		0,233		
Pendidikan		0,895		
Stress Kerja		0,012		
Kinerja				

Table 7: Statistical Test Results F (simultaneous)

From the table above it can be concluded as follows:

- The value of f square leadership (X1) is 0.233, then leadership ability (X1) in explaining performance variables (Y) is included in the Medium Effect (Medium).
- The value of f square education (X2) is 0.895, then the educational ability (X2) in explaining the variable Performance (Y) is included in the Large Effect (High).
- The value of f square work stress (X3) is 0.012, then the ability of work stress (X3) in explaining the variable Performance (Y) is included in the Small Effect (Low).
- Statistical test F on the variables of leadership, education, and work stress in the UPT Dormitory Hajj Bekasi simultaneously or together does not affect the performance

of employees in the UPT Dormitory Hajj Bekasi, because all dependent variables are greater than 0.05.

R Square

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
KINERJA (Y)	0,776	0,762

Table 8: Coefficient of Determination Test Results (R2)

The coefficient of determination (R2) is used to test the percentage change of the dependent variable (Y) caused by the independent variable (X). It can be seen that the coefficient of determination (R2) shows an R Square Adjusted number of 0.776 or 77.6%, meaning that performance variables can be explained by variables of leadership, education, and work stress. While the remaining 32.4% can be explained by other variables outside this study.

Fig 2: Path Model

From figure 2 above, it shows that Path Coefficients are the result of direct effect testing, so it can be concluded as follows:

- Leadership includes a positive impact on performance of Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory representatives with a factual t of 3.748 (p<0.002), P esteem of 0.000 is less than 0.05, meaning that there's a critical impact of leadership on employee performance at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory.
- Education includes a positive impact on the performance of the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory employees with a factual t of 7.497 (p<0.002), P esteem of 0.000 is less than 0.05, meaning that there's a critical impact of employee performance at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory.
- Work stress includes negatively impact on the performance of the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory employees with a factual t of 0.814 (p<0.002), P value of work stress is worth 0.416 more than 0.05, meaning that there's a critical impact of employee performance at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory.

Latent Variable Correlations

	Kepemimpinan	Pendidikan	Stress Kerja	Kinerja
Kepemimpinan	1,000	0,641	-0,579	0,744
Pendidikan	0,641	1,000	-0,500	0,837
Stress Kerja	-0,579	-0,500	1,000	-0,551
Kinerja	0,744	0,837	-0,551	1,000

Table 9: Correlation Coefficient

The relationship coefficient (r) is utilized to test whether or not the relationship between an autonomous variable and a subordinate variable is solid. From the table over it can be concluded that the relationship coefficient in this think about is as takes after:

- The leadership variable (X1) with the performance variable (Y) contains a relationship coefficient esteem of 0.744 (positive/+), at that point the relationship between the two factors is unidirectional, in the event that the administration variable (X1) rises at that point the execution variable (Y) will rise, and the relationship of the two factors is strong.
- The education variable (X2) with the performance variable (Y) encompasses a connection coefficient esteem of 0.837 (positive / +), at that point the relationship between the two factors is unidirectional, on the off chance that the instruction variable (X2) rises at that point the execution variable (Y) will increment, and the relationship of the two factors is exceptionally strong.
- The work stress variable (X3) with the performance variable (Y) includes a relationship coefficient esteem of -0.551 (negative/-), then the relationship between the two factors isn't within the same heading, in the event that the work push variable (X1) rises, the execution variable (Y) will diminish, and the relationship between the two factors is solid.

The results of hypothesis testing prove that the influence of leadership on employee performance at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory can be inferred from the value of the statistical testing mentioned above. Leadership variables have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory. Leaders who place too much emphasis on improving performance, may have a detrimental impact that will reduce organizational performance [9].

Based on the analysis of the data above, good leadership will make employee performance levels rise, and vice versa. In addition, based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis, the leadership variable has a coefficient value of 0.324, meaning that leadership has a relationship that is in the same direction as employee performance at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory, if the leadership variable increases, the performance variable will also increase. On the other hand, the leadership variable with the performance variable has a correlation coefficient value of 0.744 (positive/+), then the correlation of the two variables is strong.

The results of hypothesis testing prove that the effect of education on employee performance at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory can be inferred from the statistical testing values above. Educational variables have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory. Education and training on improving employee performance collectively affect employee performance and have a considerable contribution or proportion to the rise and fall of employee performance and there is a very close relationship between education and training and employee work effectiveness [10].

Based on the analysis of the data above, a good education will make the level of employee performance rise, and vice versa. In addition, based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis, the education variable has a correlation coefficient value of 0.837 (close to +1), meaning that education has a relationship in the same direction as the performance of employees at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory, if the education variable increases, the performance variable will also increase. On the other hand, the education variable with the performance variable has a correlation coefficient value of 0.597 (positive/+), hence the correlation of the two variables is strong.

The results of hypothesis testing prove that the effect of work stress on employee performance at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory, can be inferred from the statistical testing values above. The variable work stress has a negative and significant effect on employee performance at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory. This agrees with the previous journal with conclusion that work stress has a negative and significant effect on employee performance and has a very small effect on employee performance [11].

Based on the analysis of the data above, high work stress will make employee performance levels fall, and vice versa. In addition, referring to the results of multiple linear regression analysis, the work stress variable has a coefficient value of -0.065 (close to -1), meaning that work stress has a negative effect that is large enough to affect employee performance at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory, if the work stress variable rises, the performance variable will decrease. On the other hand, the work stress variable with the performance variable has a relationship coefficient value of -0.065 (negative /-), meaning that the correlation between the two variables is strong.

VI. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Based on data that has been obtained and processed with SEM PLS statistics, in research on leadership, education, and work stress on employee performance at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory, the author draws the following conclusions:

- Leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This can be proven by the results of hypothesis testing and discussion which shows that the

leadership variable has a calculated value greater than the t -table with a significance smaller than the specified level of significance. The results of the multiple linear regression analysis test of the leadership variable are the second dominant variable, meaning that leadership has a second role after education that can improve employee performance at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory if managed properly. In addition, based on the results of the correlation between the dimensions of the leadership variable has a positive coefficient value / +, it can be concluded that the relationship between the two variables is unidirectional, if the leadership variable rises, the performance variable will increase, and the correlation of the two variables is strong.

- Educational variables have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory. This can be seen from the results of hypothesis testing and discussion which shows that the educational variable has a calculated value greater than the t -table with a significance that is smaller than the specified level of significance. The results of the multiple linear regression analysis test of the education variable are the most dominant variables, meaning that education has the highest role that can improve employee performance at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory if managed properly. In addition, based on the results of the correlation between the dimensions of the education variable has a positive coefficient value / +, it can be concluded that the relationship between the two variables is unidirectional, if the education variable rises, the performance variable will increase, and the correlation of the variable is strong.
- The variable of work stress has a negative and significant effect on the performance of the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory employees and has a very small effect on employee performance. This can be seen from the results of hypothesis testing and discussion which shows that the work stress variable has a calculated value greater than the t -table with a significance that is smaller than the specified level of significance. High work stress will make employee performance levels fall, and vice versa. In addition, based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis, the work stress variable has a coefficient value that has a large enough effect to affect employee performance at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory. On the other hand, the correlation coefficient of the work stress variable with performance has a value of -0.603 (negative /-), then the relationship between the two variables is not in the same direction, if the work stress variable rises, the performance variable will decrease, and the correlation between the two variables is very weak.
- Variables of leadership, education and work stress simultaneously or together do not affect the performance of employees at the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory. This can be seen from the results of hypothesis testing and discussion which shows that the value of f square in the statistical test F shows that all variables are greater than 0.05.

Further research can examine further in the Technical Implementation Unit of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory which is different from the larger population and respondents, so that the study is even deeper about what factors affect employee performance, especially other factors or variables that have not been studied by the authors in this study, such as discipline, ethics, organizational culture and other variables.

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